

Improving Public Sector Performance through Human Capital Investment: The Role of Training and Career Development in Pariaman City, Indonesia

Novita Anggraini¹, Nidya Dudija²

^{1,2}School of Economics and Business Telkom University, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: Employee performance plays a crucial role in governance and public service. Enhancing staff performance through training and development to increase competencies in order to improve performance is one way the government is working to increase the efficacy and efficiency of public services. The firm can reap long-term benefits from investing in human resource development, so it is imperative to provide staff training and career development greater thought and assistance. The primary goal of this research is to examine the effects of training and career development on the performance of civil servants in the Pariaman City government. The respondents total are 295 civil servants from the Pariaman City Government participated in the data gathering process, which involved distributing questionnaires to them both online and offline. The Slovin formula and cluster random sampling technique were used to get the sample size. To examine data was used the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) - Partial Least Square (PLS) method. According to the study's result, training has a considerable and substansial impact on employee performance. Career development also has an influence on employee performance but has a weak correlation. Simultaneously, training and career development have impact with a percentage of 45.5% on employee performance.

KEYWORDS: Career Development, Employee Performance and Training

I. INTRODUCTION

Employee performance has a crucial role in effective and efficient government administration and public services. In the context of modern bureaucracy, the quality of public services does not only depend on systems and regulations, but depends on the knowledge, competence and attitude of employees as public servants. Therefore, the government needs to strengthen strategies and efforts to optimize employee performance through training and development to improve their competence. Inventory in human resource development is believed to provide long-term benefits for the organization so that the government needs to give more attention and assistance to employee training and career development.

Performance is the accomplishment of an individual or organization, while employee performance is the capacity of an employee to accomplish and carry out his duties in compliance with the organization's norms and standards (Ituma et al., 2024). According to Asmar & Razak (2023) employee performance is a comparison between the output that has been achieved both in quality and quantity with the standards established by the organization based on the given to employees. Performance according to Suryanto & Cahaya (2023) is the result of employee work in completing their work with the aim of managing organizational resources so that the organization's goal and mission are achieved effectively and efficiently. Employee performance is a reflection of how well employee carry out their responsibilities in line with the roles and functions that the organization has established. PermenPAN RB No. 6 of 2022 emphasizes that employee performance is one of the main pillars in realizing an effective bureaucracy, as well as being the basis for developing employee competence and performance accountability.

Continuous competency development can improve employee's performance by updating their knowledges and skills through continuous training and development. Training is an activity that is systematically structured to develop and support employee competence in carrying out their duties and encourage employee motivation, satisfaction and confidence (Ahmed et al., 2024). According to Kasmir (2019), training is a facility provided by the organization to its employees to improve knowledge, skills and behavior related to employee performance. Training's primary goals is to help people to improve their knowledge, skills, and attitudes so that they can contribute positively to improving the performance of the employees themselves and the organization. Training and development program conducted will have a meaningful benefit on the organization itself, in the form of increased performance, productivity, stability, and flexibility to change in the current digital era. In addition, in the long run, training will form a productive and adaptive work culture to changes in the current era of digital transformation.

Apart from training, employee performance can also be maintained by paying attention to employee career development. Career development is essentially a part of HR management, which seeks to increase worker effectiveness and productivity in achieving organizational goals (Mahdavikia et al, 2020). Career development is an individual's effort to improve his status in order to get a higher position and compensation (Fitrianingrum, et al. 2020). Career development programs help employees in enhancing their performance and increase their probability to get promoted to achieve the next career level in a directed manner (Gibran & Ramadani, 2021). According to Sinambela (2016) career development is a way for the organization to help employee in creating, design and constructing their career path

This research was conducted on employees in the Pariaman City government. Based on the ASN Professionalism Index (IP ASN) which measures the professionalism of ASN based on 4 dimensions, namely qualifications, competence, performance and discipline, there are significant fluctuations in the competency and performance dimensions in Pariaman City in 2020-2023. The performance dimension is the result of employee performance assessment based on employee work goals and behavior. The fluctuation in value is due to the low awareness of employees in reporting their performance, causing performance evaluation to be less than optimal. As a result, it will be difficult to identify training and competency development needs for each employee so that opportunities for training and self-development are limited. This also causes fluctuations in the value of the competency dimension as measured by training and development carried out by employees. When employees have the opportunity to develop and improve their competence, their level of job satisfaction tends to increase so that it has a positive effects on their performance. Some previous studies about training and performance show mixed results, such as research conducted by Ahmed et al. (2024), Hosen et al. (2024), Hasanah et al. (2021), Abbas et al. (2020), which showed a significant effect. Meanwhile, according to Adam et al. (2020) and Setyawati et al. (2022) and Gibran & Ramadani (2021) found that the relationship was not strong enough.

In the context of public bureaucracy, employee career development aims to improve individual capabilities in order to adapt to dynamic and complex task demands. This can be done starting from career planning, career succession, education, training, strategic position placement to promotion. Based on the BKPSDM Performance Report of Pariaman City for 2021-2023, the merit system assessment of Pariaman City is still of insufficient value, namely 191 in 2021, 207 in 2022 and 196.5 in 2023. This is because there are still several aspects that have not been fulfilled, especially in the aspect of career development. The low assessment of career development indicators is due to the lack of availability of talent pools and succession plans that meet the standards. Without a clear talent pool or competency mapping, it will be difficult to identify the potential of employees and without a clear succession plan, employees do not have a clear picture of the career path they can take in the future. This can decrease work motivation and reduce employees' desire to develop themselves. Employee desire to perform better in the hopes of being promoted to a higher position can be increased by organizations with strong career development programs (Suryanto & Cahaya, 2023). Structured career development not only increases productivity but also increases employee loyalty so that it becomes a driver of overall performance improvement. A planned and directed career development program will improve employee capabilities, create a positive work environment and ensure effective achievement of organizational targets. Ahmed et al. (2024), Hadaitana & Iqbal (2023), Sammy et al. (2023), Setyawati et al. (2022), Hasanah et al. (2021), Gibran & Ramadani (2021) explain that career development and employee performance has a favorable correlation. In contrast to the research of Suryanto & Cahaya (2023), Yuliana et al. (2024), Darmawan & Anggelina (2022) found the opposite result, that the impact of career development on employee performance is not always significant and substantial. In human resource management, career development and training go hand in hand, training serves as a short-term intervention to improve knowledge and competence while career development focuses on building long-term competencies that can support employee commitment and loyalty (Sinambela, 2016). When employees have access and opportunities to attend training, it will contribute well to their competence and knowledge so that it will affect how they complete tasks and in the organization, it will improve employee performance and can open up opportunities for employees in their career development (Hashari, et al., 2022). Gibran & Ramadani (2021) in their research found employee performance was impacted by both career development and training at the same time. This is consistent with Hasanah et al. (2021) research, which discovered a relationship between career development and training and employee performance.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Human Resource Management

The organization's most valuable asset is thought to be its human capital, which must be managed and developed properly so that they can support all activities in the organization. Edison (2016: 10) defines HRM as a management concept that focuses on employee capabilities in various strategic steps to improve and optimize employee performance in achieving organizational goals. Supriadi et al. (2022), explained that HRM contributed significantly in creating a competitive organizational edge through optimal utilization of human assets. Meanwhile, Mangkunegara (2017: 2) asserts that human resource management consists of a series of processes that organizations follow in managing its human assets such as starting from planning HR needs, recruitment, training, performance appraisal to career development. In the public sector, HRM plays an important role in shaping a bureaucracy that is professional, accountable and adaptive to change. Human resource management is key in improving public services and bureaucratic reforms that can be carried out through training, development and performance evaluation.

Performance

Performance is a crucial element that plays a significant role in deciding whether an organization is successful in reaching its objectives. In the context of government, employee performance is a crucial determinant and key indicator in the success of bureaucratic reform and public services. Mangkunegara (2017: 9) explains that performance is the outcome of each person's efforts to fulfill their responsibilities in line with the criteria established by the company. Kaeruman (2021: 8) explains that performance is the achievement of one's work within a certain period of time which is assessed based on qualitative and quantitative indicators. Meanwhile, Busro (2018: 49) explains that employee performance does not only cover the output produced, but also the work process, discipline, and employee behavior seen during work. Within government agencies, employee performance is assessed based on PAN-RB Ministerial Regulation Number 6 of 2022 which covers two main dimensions, namely employee performance targets seen from quality, quantity, time and cost and employee work behavior such as discipline, cooperation, and employee attitudes. Na-Nan et al. (2018) states the dimension of performance are (1) Job quality, which measures how well a worker's performance meets the standards and specifications that are specified, (2) Job quantity, which measures the amount of output produced by employees in the form of goods, services, and other assets in accordance with the organization's goals. (3) Job time, which is a measure of efficiency used to complete tasks.

Training

Training is an important component of human resource management that aims to improve a person's skills and knowledge in carrying out their duties (Sinambela, 2016: 170). An organization's efforts to enhance employee performance and quality as well as close the ability gap among employees are known as training. Sisca et al.,(2022: 121) states that training is a methodical, brief learning process intended to enhance employees' technical proficiency and work conduct in performing both routine and strategic tasks. According to Busro (2018: 203) training is a tool in organizations that is useful for changing employee performance in achieving organizational growth and success. Hadi & Djalil (2020) explain that training is a program in an organization that is expected to encourage someone to improve their abilities in their field as well as general knowledge and understanding of the organization as a whole. Training is a strategic mechanism to reduce gaps in employee competencies and abilities and strengthen employee capacity in the face of evolving changes and bureaucratic reforms. According to Dhar (2015), there are three dimensions of training. That are (1) Easy Training Access, which indicate by Information on the number and kind of classes offered by the organization, Access to the classes offered by the organization and the number and type of classes already meet the requirements. (2) Training support, which indicated by Manager or leaders support, colleague support, communication ease related to training and easy use training procedure.

Career Development

According to Busro (2018: 274) career development is the vertical development of a person in the staffing structure through promotions, further training, study assignments, mutations to strategic position placements in accordance with employee competencies and abilities. Career development is the result of synergy between the personal aspirations of employees and organizations as part of a strategy to create competitive and highly competitive resources (Supriadi, 2022: 150). In government, based on Law number 5 of 2014 concerning ASN management, employee career development is carried out through a meritocracy approach or merit system that makes qualifications, competence and integrity the basis for appointment to positions with the aim of ensuring that each worker has an equal change to success in certain positions and positions in accordance with their contribution to the

organization. Career development carried out by the organization such as learning assignments, training, benchmarking, courses, workshops, leadership training and various other efforts. Mustaqim & Sary (2022) explain the dimension of career development are according to simamora (2006) there are (1) career planning, which indicated by career goal to be achieved, employee involvement in choosing career path and career goals and readiness in preparing career planning. (2) Communication of career opportunities, The existence of a career path, Matching employee expectations with career opportunities, Career development programme.

Research framework and model hypotesis

The effects of Training on employee performance

Training is viewed as a type of strategic investment in a certain organization. In addition, training and development programs are crucial for increasing employee motivation, which, in turn, might encourage them to stay in the organization rather than looking for work opportunities elsewhere (Mohd et al., 2020). When given the opportunity to participate in training, employees gradually grow in knowledge that contributes to their increased productivity. Mamy et al. (2020) explain, facilities of training that organization gave to employees can increas and improve their performance. This is supported by research conducted by Ahmed et al. (2024), Hosen et al. (2024), Hasanah et al. (2021), and Abbas et al. (2020), which indicates that training has a significant impact on employees' work performance. However, different results are showed on the study of Gibran & Ramadani (2021), they found a weak corelation between training and employee performance.

H1 : There is a correlation between training and employee performance.

The effect of career development on employee performance

According to Setiawati et al. (2023), career development has a significant role in promoting individual advancement toward higher career levels and enhancing professionalism at work. In line with their duties and functions in the workplace, career development gives workers the chance to increase their competencies, sharpen their skills, and broaden their knowledge. Employees will be more driven and dedicated to their work in order to enhance their performance when they perceive that their careers are progressing and developing (Ituma et al., 2024). In addition to enhancing employee professionalism, this promotes greater motivation and loyalty at work. To put it another way, focused and methodical career development may produce a workforce that is flexible, creative, and equipped to handle the ever-increasing demands of the workplace.

H2 : There is a correlation between career development and employee performance.

The effect of training and career development on employee performance

Hosen et al. (2024) clarify that having a defined career development program inside the company can boost employee performance, which is reinforced by training that can boost performance. Employees that get the chance to participate in training will be more competent and knowledgeable, which will improve how they carry out their tasks and obligations within the company. Employee performance will increase as a result, and professional growth possibilities may become available. In their study, Gibran & Ramadani (2021) discovered that employee performance was impacted by both career growth and training at the same time. This is in line with the research of Hasanah et al. (2021), Hashari et al. (2022) which found that the existence of training and career development funds in the organisation can improve employee performance.

H3 : There is a correlation between training and career development on employee performance.

Based on the theory, previous research and mindset that has been explained, it can be formulated that training (X1) and career development (X2) are thought to have an influence on employee performance (y) as the dependent variable described in the following research framework

Figure 1. Research Framework
Source: processed by researchers, 2025

III. RESEARCH METHODE

This research uses quantitative methods carried out through a deductive approach by using theory as a basis for answering research questions and formulating hypotheses. The research data was collected through distributing online and offline closed questionnaires to 295 civil servants within the Pariaman City government which were grouped into several groups using the Cluster random sampling method. Each instrument was measured using a five-point Likert scale and analyzed using the Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) - Partial Least Square (PLS) method with the help of SmartPLS 4.0.

IV. RESULT

Uji Measurement model (Outer model)

Figure 2. Measurement Construct Model
Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Validity Test

Based on the results of the study, these indicators have met the criteria of discrimination and convergent validity. The outer loading level above 0.7 and the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value above 0.5 are required to show convergent validity. The outerloading of this study has exceeded 0.7 as seen in Figure 1 and the AVE of each indicator, namely performance 0.708, training 0.613 and career development 0.638, has also exceeded 0.5, which shows that each indicator can accurately measure its construct.

Discriminant validity has also met the criteria, as indicated by the results of cross loading and comparison between constructs using the Fornell-Larcker AVE criterion. Each construct has a greater correlation value with its own indicators than with other constructs, so it can be concluded that the instruments used in this study are valid.

Table 1. Cross Loading Value

Indicator	Performance	Training	Career Deveopment	Desc
K1.1	0,820	0,549	0,513	Valid
K1.2	0,890	0,589	0,455	Valid
K1.3	0,778	0,485	0,422	Valid
K1.4	0,747	0,529	0,419	Valid
K1.5	0,874	0,542	0,404	Valid
K2.2	0,881	0,594	0,442	Valid
K2.3	0,769	0,550	0,485	Valid
K2.4	0,875	0,568	0,444	Valid
K3.1	0,850	0,486	0,409	Valid
K3.2	0,851	0,570	0,465	Valid
K3.3	0,886	0,550	0,491	Valid
K3.4	0,863	0,605	0,534	Valid
P1.1	0,404	0,703	0,591	Valid
P1.3	0,379	0,701	0,570	Valid
P2.1	0,433	0,763	0,624	Valid
P2.2	0,424	0,713	0,555	Valid
P2.3	0,501	0,814	0,609	Valid
P2.4	0,536	0,804	0,576	Valid
P2.5	0,577	0,761	0,568	Valid
P2.6	0,447	0,755	0,680	Valid
P3.1	0,590	0,750	0,326	Valid
P3.10	0,402	0,747	0,502	Valid
P3.11	0,450	0,801	0,546	Valid
P3.12	0,492	0,795	0,533	Valid
P3.2	0,650	0,817	0,454	Valid
P3.3	0,599	0,825	0,447	Valid
P3.4	0,535	0,825	0,445	Valid
P3.5	0,579	0,831	0,403	Valid
P3.6	0,410	0,768	0,498	Valid
P3.8	0,541	0,817	0,509	Valid
P3.9	0,627	0,858	0,516	Valid
PK1.2	0,462	0,494	0,709	Valid

Indicator	Performance	Training	Career Deveopment	Desc
PK1.3	0,392	0,430	0,810	Valid
PK1.4	0,391	0,541	0,751	Valid
PK1.5	0,493	0,450	0,711	Valid
PK1.6	0,554	0,511	0,752	Valid
PK2.1	0,325	0,452	0,840	Valid
PK2.2	0,308	0,454	0,816	Valid
PK2.3	0,401	0,531	0,842	Valid
PK2.4	0,429	0,588	0,813	Valid
PK2.5	0,413	0,556	0,829	Valid
PK2.6	0,363	0,527	0,822	Valid
PK2.7	0,422	0,567	0,859	Valid
PK2.8	0,522	0,623	0,809	Valid

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Table 2. AVE fornell-lacker criterion Value

	Performance	Training	Career Deveopment
Performance	0,842		
Training	0,658	0,783	
Career Deveopment	0,545	0,656	0,799

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Reliability test

Meanwhile, in terms of reliability, the instruments in this study proved to be consistent and reliable. This is indicated by the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability values which are above the specified threshold of >0.7, which means that all variables have a very good level of reliability in measuring the intended concept.

Table 3. Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability Test Results

No.	Variabel	Cronbach's alpha	Composite Reliability	Description
1	Performance	0,962	0,967	Reliabel
2	Training	0,965	0,968	Reliabel
3	Career Deveopment	0,953	0,958	Reliabel

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Analysing the structural model, or inner model

The inner model (structural model) test is designed to see the level of influence of the relationship between constructs measured in this study by analysing collinearity, coefficient of determination (R square), F square, predictive relevance (Q2), goodness of fit index (GOF Index), and hypothesis testing.

Collinearity

Table 4. Inner VIF Test Results

	Performance	Training	Career Development
Performance			
Training	1,757		
Career Development	1,757		

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Collinearity which is analysed through the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. The test results show that all independent variables have VIF values below 5, which indicates the absence of multicollinearity problems. Thus, each independent variable can be used simultaneously in predicting the dependent variable without negatively affecting each other.

Coefficient of Determination (R²)

Table 5. R Square Result

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Performance	0,455	0,452

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Testing the coefficient of determination (R²) shows that the training and career development variables together are able to explain variations in employee performance by 45.5%. This value is in the medium category, which means that this model is quite capable of explaining the influence of the independent variables on performance, although there are still other factors outside the model that also influence.

f Square (f²)

Table 6. F Square Result

	Performance	Training	Career Development
Performance			
Training	0,290		
Career Development	0,042		

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Analysis of the f² value is used to determine the amount of contribution of each independent variable to the dependent variable separately. The results show that training has a moderate effect on performance, while career development has a weak effect. This indicates that training has a more dominant role in driving performance improvement than career development.

Q Square (Q²)

Table 7. Q Square Result

	Q ² predict
Performance	0,428

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

the predictive relevance (Q²) test shows that the model has relevant predictive ability on the performance variable. Despite being in the weak category, the positive Q² value indicates that the model still has adequate predictive power.

Goodness of fit indeks (GOF Indeks)

Goodness of fit is a test of the overall combined fit of the model using the goodness of fit index value obtained through the following formula:

$$GOF = \sqrt{\text{Communnality} \times R^2}$$

According to Ghozali (2015) the GOF value of 0.1 is categorized as low, 0.25 is categorized as medium and 0.36 is categorized as high. The following are the GOF index results obtained from this study:

Table 8. Goodness of fit Indeks Result

Average Communnality	Average R Square	R	GOF Index	Category
0,653	0,455		0,545	Tinggi

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

The Goodness of Fit (GoF) Indeks measurement which reflects the overall suitability of the model shows a value of 0.545 which is in the high category. This indicates that in general the model built in this study is appropriate and feasible to use to explain the phenomenon studied.

Hipotesis Test

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine the extent to which the relationship between variables in this research model is statistically significant. This process is done by looking at the t-statistic value, p-value, and path coefficient (original sample) obtained through Partial Least Squares (PLS) analysis. The following are the results of hypothesis testing from this study:

Table 9. Hipotesis Test Result

	Original sample (O)	T statistics	T Tabel	P values	Description
Training -> Performance Career Development -> Performance	0.527	5.579	1,968	0.000	Accepted
	0.200	2.193	1,968	0.028	Accepted

Source: Researcher processed data on smart PLS 4, 2025

Training has a significant effect on employee performance (H1)

Based on table 9, it can be seen that the T statistic value of the training variable on career development has a value of 5.579 which is greater than the T table value of 1.968 and the original sample value of 0.527. This means that the better the training provided, the higher the performance that can be shown by employees. original sample which is positive reinforces the existence of a direct and unidirectional relationship between these two variables so that the first hypothesis (H1) of this study is accepted.

Career Development has a significant effect on employee performance (H2)

Based on table 9, the t statistic value of the career development variable on performance has a value greater than the t table value, namely 2.193 > 1.968 and the original sample value of 0.200. The sample oroginal obtained is positive, which indicates that career development still contributes to improving performance, although its effect is not as strong as training. This indicates that career aspects remain an important factor in improving employee performance. so that the second hypothesis (H2) of this study is accepted.

Training and career development have a significant effect on employee performance (H3)

A simultaneous test, Hypothesis 3 (H3) examines how development and training affect employee performance. Ghozali (2018: 98) states that simultaneous tests are used to ascertain the combined impact of independent variables on the dependent variable. This can be done by examining the computed F value and F table, using the criterion that if F count > F table, the hypothesis is accepted, and if F count < F table, the hypothesis is rejected. The F table value is 3.027 based on the F distribution table for the number of independent variables (k) 2 and the number of samples (n) 295.

The following is the formula for finding the F value:

$$F \text{ hitung} = \frac{R^2(n - k - 1)}{(1 - R^2)k}$$

Ket :

- R² = R Square
- n = Number of Samples
- k = number of dependent variables

The following is the calculated F value for this study:

$$F \text{ hitung} = \frac{R^2(n - k - 1)}{(1 - R^2)k}$$
$$F \text{ hitung} = \frac{0.455 (295 - 2 - 1)}{(1 - 0,455)2}$$
$$F \text{ hitung} = 121,889$$

The value of F count (121.889) > F table (3.027) indicates that hypothesis 3 is accepted based on the computations above. This indicates that the dependent variable is influenced by the independent variables in this study. So, it can be said that career development and training both affect how well civil officers in the Pariaman City Government perform.

V. DISCUSSION

Analysis of the Effect of Training on the Performance of Civil Servants in the Pariaman City Government Environment

Based on the results of hypothesis testing in table 8, the effect of training on employee performance has a statistical t value of 5.597 > t table 1.968, so hypothesis 1 (H1) is accepted. The results of this study indicate that training has a significant effect on the performance of civil servants in the pariaman city government. Based on table 8, training has an f square value of 0.29, which means that training has an effect on performance but has a weak effect.

This research is consistent with the research of Abbas et al. (2020) which discovered a relationship between employee performance and training. To accomplish their objectives, organizations must create policies that provide training and equitable support for their human resources. Additionally, Otoo & Mishra (2018) demonstrate that employee performance and training have a substantial impact, which he claims validates Becker's (1964, 1993) notion that training is an investment that helps people become more productive. Arwab et al. (2022) also found a favorable correlation between training and employee performance, employee performance is influenced by knowledge, skills, and abilities that employees can obtain through training and development. Training can increase the level of employees in the organization by providing more effective and efficient performance (Khan et al., 2020). Employees are more motivated to achieve at their highest level for the organization when their employers actively support their training and development (Yimam, 2022). Hasanah et al. (2021), Sari & Suherman (2021) also discovered a strong correlation between employee performance and training.

In contrast to research conducted by Hamzah & Resdiana (2023) which shows employee performance is not much impacted by training. Sulu et al. (2022) found raining impairs performance. Hosen et al. (2024), Setiawati et al. (2023), Adam et al. (2020), Manoppo et al. (2021), Kosali (2023), Khansha & Indiyati (2022) also found no correlation was seen between employee performance and training.

Analysis of the Influence of Career Development on the Performance of Civil Servants within the Pariaman City Government

Based on table 11, the effect of career development on performance has a statistical t value of 2.193 > t table 1.968, so hypothesis 2 (H2) is accepted. Table 8 shows that career development has an f square value of 0.042, which means that career development has an influence on employee performance but is in the weak category.

This research is in line with research conducted by Hamzah & Resdiana (2023) that a career development program can improve employee performance and help employees achieve the next career level in a directed manner. Wanjiru & Ombui (2021) also found a positive influence between career development and employee performance. According to Otoo & Mishra (2018) career development can help the partnership of organizations and their employees and enrich knowledge, skills and improve individual abilities and competencies. According to Sammy et al. (2023) career development can help employee performance get better. Career development is a very important practice in organizations and must be included in the policy (Ondere & Makhamura, 2022). Organizations have a very important role in employee career development because the organization is a place where employees can develop their careers.

Hosen et al. (2024), Setiawati et al. (2023), Hasanah et al. (2021), Adam et al. (2020), Manoppo et al. (2021), Syarahil & Wahyuningtyas (2023) also found a significant influence between cash development on employee performance.

In contrast to the research of Suryanto & Cahaya (2023) which found that career development has no significant effect on performance. Kosali (2023), Hapsoro et al. (2022), Aidah & Ratnasari (2020) also found that career development has no effect on performance.

Analysis of the Effect of Training and Career Development on the Performance of Civil Servants within the Pariaman City Government

Based on the results of calculations regarding the simultaneous test of the effect of training and career development on performance has a calculated F value of $121.889 > F$ table 3.0 then hypothesis 3 (H3) is accepted. Table 7 shows the R square value of 0.455, which means that training and career development career development has an influence on employee performance by 45.5% and the rest is influenced by other variables not examined in this study. In line with research conducted Nabilah et al. (2023) which found the influence between training and career development on performance, which is 34.1%. This is in line with research conducted by Hashari et al. (2022) which shows that training and career development have an influence on employee performance of 42.4% and the rest is influenced by other variables. Ichsan & Laksana (2023) also found an influence between training and career development on employee performance by 39.7%. Hamzah & Resdiana (2023), Hasanah et al. (2021), Gibran & Ramadani (2021), Jafar (2020) also show the effect of training and career development on employee performance. Mohd et al. (2020) explain that assessing training needs and further career development needs to be done to improve employee performance. According to Hosen et al. (2024) training and career development are important aspects of employee performance. Manoppo et al. (2021), explain that training and career development have a strong relationship so that they can improve employee performance).

VI. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be concluded that training and career development have a significant influence on increasing employee productivity in the Pariaman City Government. In short, training is the most important factor in determining work efficiency, employee satisfaction, and national professionalism. Conversely, career development also has a positive impact although its contribution is not as significant as training, which shows the importance of well-structured and thorough career research in improving employee performance. Simultaneously, these two variables can explain employee's work, indicating that human resource management strategies that integrate training with karir development can be an effective way to create productive and resolute birokrasi. As a result, there needs to be a strategic integration between training and karir development in order to implement professional, responsible, and high-quality public service.

VII. SUGGESTION

Based on the explanation, theory and conclusions obtained from the results of processing and analysis in this study, the authors try to submit several suggestions to serve as input in this study. First, Training is proven to have a significant contribution to employee performance so that the Pariaman city government is advised to pay more attention and provide better support for employees to attend training so as to support improved employee performance. Second, career development also has a contribution to employee performance so that the Pariaman city government is advised to re-evaluate the talent pool, succession planning in employee career management in Pariaman city in order to boost morale, motivation and create a competitive but healthy work climate and more in line with employee expectations. Third, Investment in human resource development will have a long-term impact on the organization so that the Pariaman city government needs to pay more attention and provide support for employee training and career development. Finally, based on the results of this study, the effect of the dependent variable on the dependent variable is still in the moderate category, which is only 45.5%, this shows that the effect of training and career development variables on performance is only 45.5% so researchers suggest using other dependent variables that may have a greater influence on performance such as employee engagement, organizational culture, transformational leadership, and psychological empowerment. This variable is still relatively rarely researched in depth in the context of government agencies.

REFERENCES

1. Abbas, N., Ashiq, U., & Abbas, A. (2020). Training and Employee Performance: Mediating Role of Job Satisfaction in Civil Society Organizations of Pakistan. *Journal of Accounting and Finance in Emerging Economies*, 6(4), 1041-1050. <https://doi.org/10.26710/jafee.v6i4.1458>
2. Adam, M., Juita, R., & Djalil, M. A. (2020). The Effect of Competence, Education and Training on Career Development and Its Impact on Employees' Performance in Aceh Civil Service Agency, Indonesia. *East African Scholars Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, 03(03), 265-269. <https://doi.org/10.36349/EASJEBM.2020.v03i03.038>
3. Ahmed, S., Ashrafi, D. M., Ahmed, R., Ahmed, E., & Azim, M. (2024). How employee engagement mediates the training and development and work-life balance towards job performance of the private banks? *TQM Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/TQM-10-2023-0316>
4. Aidah, S., & Ratnasari, S. L. (2020). The effect of training, career development, and communication on employee performance pt. Telekomindo primakarya. *Journal of Trias Politika*, 4(2), 122-135.
5. Arwab, M., Ansari, J. A. N., Azhar, M., & Ali, M. A. (2022). Exploring the influence of training and development on employee's performance: Empirical evidence from the Indian tourism industry. *Management Science Letters*, 12(2), 89-100. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2021.10.004>
6. Asmar, & Razak, St. R. (2023). The Influence of Human Resource Development Competencies and Organizational Culture on Employee Performance at BPJS Ketenagakerjaan Regional Office of Sulawesi Maluku. *Journal of Management Science (JMS)*, 4(2), 2023. Darmawan, A., & Angelina, Y. (2022). Motivation, Job Training, Career Development and Self Efficacy on Employee Performance. *Journal of Management Science*, 12. <https://doi.org/10.32502/jimn.v12i1.5142>
7. Busro, M. (2018). *Theories of Human Resource Management*. Jakarta: Prenadamedia Group
8. Dhar, R. L. (2015). Service quality and the training of employees: The mediating role of organizational commitment. *Tourism Management*, 46, 419-430. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tourman.2014.08.001>
9. Edison, Emron, et al. 2016 *Human Resource Management*. Alfabeta. Bandung
10. Gibran, N., & Ramadani, D. (2021). The Effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance. *Almana: Journal of Management and Business*, 5(3), 407-415. <https://doi.org/10.36555/almana.v5i3.1680>
11. Ghozali, I. 2015. *Application of Multivariate Analysis with SPSS Program*. Semarang: Diponegoro University Publishing Agency.
12. Hair, J. F. et. al. 2017. *A Primer on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM)*. SAGE Publications, Los Angeles
13. Hadaitana, D., & Iqbal, M. A. (2023). The Effect Of Training And Development on Employee Performance With Mediation of Employee Satisfaction. *International Journal of Advance Multidisciplinary E-ISSN: 2829-6192, p-ISSN: 2829-6184 DOI: https://doi.org/10.38035/Ijam.V1i4, 01(4), 436-447. https://doi.org/10.38035/ijam.v1i4*
14. Hadi, N., & Djalil, M. A. (2020). *Corresponding Author: Muslim A Djalil The Influence of Training Dimensions for Employees on the Quality of Service of Bank Mandiri Offices in Aceh Province, Indonesia with Organizational Commitment as a Mediating Variable. <https://doi.org/10.36349/easjebm.2020.v03i01.008>
15. Hamzah, M., & Resdiana, E. (2023). The Effect of Training and Career Development Regarding Employee Performance at PT Sinar Dunia. *Journal of Public Corner Fisip Wiraraja University*, 18(2), 45-57.
16. Hapsoro, B. V., Tamba, M., Suratmi, T., & Nurminingsih. (2022). The Effect of Motivation, Training, and Career Development on Employee Performance of PT Bhinneka Life Indonesia in Jakarta. *Journal of Administration and Management*, 12(2).
17. Hardani, Nur Hikmatul Auliya, Ms., Helmina Andriani, G., Roushandy Asri Fardani, Ms., Jumari Ustiawaty, Mp, Evi Fatmi Utami, Ms., Dhika Juliana Sukmana, A., Rahmatul Istiqomah, R., Oleh, D., Science Library Editor, C., & Abadi, H. (2020). *Qualitative & Quantitative Research Methods*. CV. Science Library.
18. Hasanah, N., Perizade, B., Widiyanti, M., & Adam, M. (2021). How to Cite Effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance at PT. Bank Mandiri (Persero) Tbk. Regional Retail Collection and Recovery Units Region II / Sumatra 2. *International Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(2), 211-219. <https://doi.org/10.31295/ijss.v4n2.1702>

19. Hashari, A., Nadeak, B., Karawang Ji Ronggowaluyo, S. H., & Timur, T. (2022). Effect Of Training And Career Development On Performance Civil Services Regional Secretariat. *Journal of Social Humanities*, 13(2), 139-144.
20. Hosen, S., Hamzah, S. R. ah, Arif Ismail, I., Noormi Alias, S., Faiq Abd Aziz, M., & Rahman, M. M. (2024). Training & development, career development, and organizational commitment as the predictor of work performance. *Heliyon*, 10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heliyon.2023.e23903>
21. Ichsan, R. M., & Laksana, T. R. N. P. (2023). The Effect of Career Development and Training on Employee Performance at the Sukabumi Regency Transportation Office. *Ekonomeia Journal*, XII (01), 20-44.
22. Ituma, O. A., Agu, S. U., Ozo, F. K., Chinweike, O. A., & Onwe, J. C. (2024). The Impact of Career Development on Employee Performance in the Civil Service Sector: A Nigerian Context. *Journal of Chinese Human Resource Management*, 15(1), 42-63. <https://doi.org/10.47297/wspchrmWSP2040-800504.20241501>
23. Jafar, A. (2020). The effect of training and career development on employee performance at the bkpsdm office kab. Gowa (study of BKPSDM employees at the regent's office kab. Gowa). *Journal of Islamic Economics and Business*, 5(1), 1-9. <http://journal.iaimsinjai.ac.id/index.php/adz-dzahab>
24. Khan, M. Y., Mushtaq, J., & Naz, S. (2020). Impact of Training and Development on Job Satisfaction and Job Performance with Moderating Effect of Person Job Fit. *University of Wah Journal of Management Sciences*, 4(1), 1-20.
25. Khansha, L., & Indiyati, D. (2022). The Effect of Work Training and Physical Work Environment on the Performance of Millennial Generation Employees (Case Study of BPJS Ketenagakerjaan, Regional Office of Sumbagut). *Proceedings of the 3rd Asia Pacific International Conference on Industrial Engineering and Operations Management*.
26. Kosali, Y. A. (2023). The Effect of Training and Career Development on Employee Performance with Employee Engagement as an Intervening Variable (Case Study on Employees of Lembaga Sinergi Sriwijaya Peduli). *Tirtayasa EKONOMIKA*, 18(2), 114-147. www.hukumonline.com
27. Mahdavia, A., Nugroho, A. A., & Wibawa, D. P. (2024). Holistic journal of management research the influence of job training and career development on the performance of civil servants (pns) of the tourism culture and youth sports office of the bangka belitung islands province. *Holistic Journal of Management Research*, 2. <http://journal.ubb.ac.id/index.php/holistic/management>
28. Mangkunegara. (2017). *Corporate Human Resource Management*. Teenage Workshop.
29. Manoppo, I. D., Koleangan, R. A. M., & Uhing, Y. (2021). The effect of training, and career development on employee performance at pt. Unilever indonesia. Tbk in Manado. *Journal of Economic Research, Management, Business and Accounting*, 9 (1). <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.35794/emba.9.1.2021.32164>
30. Mohd, I. H., Julan, J., Hisham, T. B., & Besar, T. (2020). Strategic Training And Development: The Impact On Employees' Performance. *Journal of International Business, Economics and Entrepreneurship*, 5(2), 2550-1429.
31. Mustaqim, M. I., & Sary, F. P. (2022). Role of Career Development and Job Satisfaction for Employee Engagement for Start-ups.
32. Nabilah, A. V., Roswaty, & Ulum, M. B. (2023). The Effect of Job Training and Career Development on Employee Performance at PT Alita Praya Mitra Palembang. *EMT KITA Journal*, 7(4), 1448-1458. <https://doi.org/10.35870/emt.v7i4.1785>
33. Na-Nan, K., Chairasit, K., & Pukkeeree, P. (2018). Factor analysis-validated comprehensive employee job performance scale. *International Journal of Quality and Reliability Management*, 35(10), 2436-2449. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJQRM-06-2017-0117>
34. Ondere, A. B., & Makhamara, F. (2022). Career Development And Employee Performance In The Ministry Of Interior And Co-Ordination Of National Government In Nairobi City County, Kenya. *Strategic Journals*, 2, 666-677. www.strategicjournals.com
35. Otoo, F. N. K., & Mishra, M. (2018). Measuring the impact of human resource development (HRD) practices on employee performance in small and medium scale enterprises. *European Journal of Training and Development*, 42(7-8), 517-534. <https://doi.org/10.1108/EJTD-07-2017-0061>
36. Pattnaik, S., & Pattnaik, S. (2021). Exploring employee performance dimensionality in Indian public sector units. *International Journal of Productivity and Performance Management*, 70(3), 657-674. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJPPM-08-2019-0374>

37. Sammy, O. M., Ejumudo, T., & Kelly b.o Ejumudo. (2023). Career development and employees' performance in selected universities in delta state. *International Journal of Innovation in Social and Policy Issues*, ISSN 5670-5668, 10(2).
38. Samsuddin, H. (2018). EMPLOYEE PERFORMANCE: A Review of the Dimensions of Leadership Style, Organizational Culture and Organizational Commitment. *INDOMEDIA PUSTAKA*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/371139163>
39. Sari, D. P., & Suherman, E. (2021). The effect of work training and work discipline on performance of pt. Plasindo sustainable karawang. *International Journal of Accounting, Taxation, and Business*, 2(2), 2021. <https://journal.unsika.ac.id/index.php/IJATB>
40. Setiawati, W., Maulida, W., Rusliana, I., & Abhipraya, F. A. (2023). The Effects of Competency, Training, and Career Development on Employee Performance at i3L. *Journal of Education Management Science*, 9(02), 221-234. <https://doi.org/10.32678/tarbawi.v9i01.9250>
41. Setyawati, N. W., Woelandari, D. S., & Muhammad Richo Rianto. (2022). Career Development, Motivation and Promotion on Employee Performance. *East Asian Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 1(9), 1957-1970. <https://doi.org/10.55927/eajmr.v1i9.1453>
42. Sinambela, L. P. (2016). *Human Resource Management (I)*. PT Bumi Aksara.
43. Sisca, Dudija, N., Indiyati, D., Sinaga, D. sariani, Sary, F. P., Wulansari, P., & Rahmasari, L. F. (n.d.). *Industrial and Organizational Psychology*.
44. Sulu, A. H. C., Mangantar, M., & Taroreh, R. (2022). The effect of training, career development, and leadership style on employee performance at the tomohon city regional education and training personnel board. *EMBA Journal*, 10(2), 560-568.
45. Supriadi, A., Ani Kusumaningsih, C., Kohar, M., Andri Priadi, M., Andi Yusniar Mendo, M., Lisda Asi SPd, M. L., Robiyati Podungge, Ms., Afriyana Amelia Nuryadin, M. H., Agus Hakri Bokingo, M., & Fiesty Utami, Ms. (2022). *HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT (I)*. Tahta Media Group.
46. Suryanto, S., & Cahaya, Y. F. (2023). The Role of Career Development, Work Environment and Compensation in Improving Employee Performance Pt Bridgestone Tire Indonesia Bekasi. In *Management Research Studies Journal Volume (Vol. 4, Issue 1)*. <https://journal.perbanas.id/index.php/mrsjhttps://journal.perbanas.id/index.php/mrsjhttps://journal.perbanas.id/index.php/mrsj> 26
47. Syarahil, J. B., & Wahyuningtyas, R. (2023). Managing Career Development and Discipline as Performance Improvement Factors. *Proceedings of the International Conference on Sustainable Collaboration in Business, Technology, Information, and Innovation (SCBTII 2023)*, *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research* 265, 113-127. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-94-6463-292-7_8
48. Wanjiru, J. N., & Ombui, k. (2021). Effect of Career Development on Employee Performance at the Aga Khan University Hospital. *Journal of Human Resource and Relationship*, 1(1), 17-24.
49. Yimam, M. H. (2022). Impact of training on employees performance: A case study of Bahir Dar university, Ethiopia. *Cogent Education*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186X.2022.2107301>
50. Yuliana, I., Management, K., Economics, F., & Business, D. (2024). Value Scientific Journal of Financial and Business Accounting The Effect of Career Development, Job Stress, and Work Motivation on Employee Performance (Case Study at Hospital in Salatiga City). *Scientific Journal of Financial and Business Accounting E-ISSN: 2723-6951*, 4(2), 220-236.

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